

The Craftsmanship As Reflected in the Selected Novels of Patrick White

OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 7

Special Issue : 1

Month : July

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-2645

Impact Factor: 4.110

Citation:

Manjula, V. ..., and S. Ramesh. "The Craftsmanship As Reflected in the Selected Novels of Patrick White." *Shanlax International Journal of English*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 162–64.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3457059>

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Abstract

Riders in the Chariot, Patrick White's sixth novel, was published in the year, after Voss and before The Solid Mandala. The novel is outstanding for its wide-ranging content, and once again White became the Miles Franklin Award for it. On the other hand, with the publication of this novel White instigated to be seen as one of the great artists of Australia.

The boy was much closer to his mother. He could always see her in his mind's eye, "where she sat very still and clear. For Mordecai, his mother remained a sculptured figure. She was a fashionable woman continuously changing identities. But his memory presented her as a single image. Though he was inclined towards her, it is not that he didn't love and honour his good father. But though Moshe Himmelfarb was very kind and generous, he did not have much influence upon his son. They used to chat and laugh together, or share views on the beauties of Goethe or other poets.

Malke Himmelfarb was a kind lady. She would visit the rather smelly, frightening houses of the poor, and take presents for them. She examined their children, for ailments, and tested their knowledge of God. She used to scrub the floors, which were neglected by the sick, a very unique quality that she possessed. She was also interested in writing letters to her relatives in her free time.

Himmelfarb was not ignorant of his religion, rather he was a Sceptic Religion, like a winter overcoat, grew oppressive and superfluous as spring developed into summer, and the natural sources of warmth were gradually revealed. In spite of that, the love and respect that he had was everlasting. To develop some confidence in Judaism and the scriptures, his mother had arranged a special tutor for him. Cantor Katzmann, who taught him Hebrew alphabets, and he began shortly to write phrases, and recite prayers. Cantor himself was a humble man. He had several squint eyed children. He was a man of short height and his pupil loved him in memory, more than he had respected him in life.

Himmelfarb had joined the gymnasium at the age of ten. He knew many languages other than English, like Greek, Latin, and French; however, he preferred the English language. He was a brilliant student and had got many prizes in school. The Father at school used to call him not by his Jewish name, but Martin. He believed that Martin would surely become a man of some importance. On the other hand, his mother hoped that her child would be remembered as a man of faith. His triumph made him proud, shy, exalted, indifferent, explosively hilarious and incommunicative of his true feelings.

In the closed and ugly house, among relatives and friends, enlightened spiritually by the love and care of God, Mordecai accepted the pattern of his religion and race. But in addition to that there was an outside world, which his mother feared, would tempt her child. But his father yearned for it, and when the silent boy grew into a bony, rasping youth, he became absolutely aware of it too. He made regular attempts to solve his own dilemmas.

A dreadful event took place in Himmelfarb's life when the Nazis raided his house; while he sought refuge in a friend's house at night his wife was seized by the Gestapo and was never seen again. He was extremely disturbed and blamed himself for this tragedy, he thought he had betrayed Reha. He was so broken that he even attempted suicide and finally surrendered to the Nazi authorities. He was sent to the gas chamber where he narrowly escaped death, and found himself on a Kibbutz with his distant relatives in the Middle East.

During a conversation Miss Hare and Himmelfarb had expressed the view that when the cruel hands of evil destroy someone there will be some kind of earthly consolation, like grass grows again after a fire. Miss Hare, said, "But the earth is wonderful. It is all we have. It has brought me back when, otherwise, I should have died." (14) One can call it the concept of "Re-birth" or metamorphosis, which is there in Hindu philosophy. Rebirth does take place but it depends upon the Karma. If someone has done a good deed then life after rebirth will be fine otherwise one has to pay retribution for the evil deed after reincarnation.

Himmelfarb's settlement in Australia was to serve the Motherland. There he met Mrs Godbold, the good mother, and Mrs Flack, the demonic mother. They were both opposite sides of the same coin. Mrs Godbold was the nourisher and Mrs Flack was the destroyer. This pattern of dualistic figures or splitting the character into two, was seen in the characters of Malke and Reha in this novel, and Laura and Rose Portion, Voss and Mr. Bonner in Voss. This is simply because, the author is compelled to keep the psychological forces in tension, even if he separates the fictional characters. Himmelfarb was loved by Mrs Godbold and harassed by Mrs Flack. Like Malke and Himmelfarb, mother and wife of Mordecai Himmelfarb, Mrs Godbold was also a spiritual kind of woman. Her notion of spirituality was very clearly expressed in her favourable hymn.

Mrs Godbold's religion was not Christianity, neither was Himmelfarb's Judaism. He is the pagan worship of the earth spirit, and his is the animus compulsion of sonship. For Mrs Godbold he was equivalent to the Messiah himself, a modern day chariot driver of the heavens, sent by God. Mrs Flack, who is said to be the dark side of the Goddess, always remained hidden behind the scenes. Throughout the novel she remained a weak figure, she was the mistress of condemnation, but Himmelfarb was unaware of the truth, while he enjoyed the attention of the good mother of Mrs Godbold. There is a similarity between Mrs Godbold and Reha in the sense that both were ready to bear the burden of all the sins of their husbands in return for them becoming religious.

Tom Godbold was reduced to helplessness before the greater forces of the Mother Goddess. Ruth Godbold held him on her breast. She buoyed him up on that dark sea. He floated in it, a human body, soothed by a mystery which was more than he could attempt to solve.

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